

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Islamov Abror Zafarovich

“G’AZNACHILIK IJROSI SHAROITIDA DAVLAT XARIDLARI

TIZIMINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH MASALALARI”

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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